

SMART CRAWLER: A TWO-STAGE CRAWLER FOR EFFICIENTLY HARVESTING DEEP-WEB INTERFACES

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ABSTRACT

Deep web growing at a very fast pace, lot of speculations in techniques this techniques has been added that help efficiently locate deep-web interfaces. However, due to the large volume of web resources and the dynamic nature of deep web, achieving wide coverage and high efficiency is a challenging issue. In this paper author has proposed a two-stage framework, namely Smart Crawler, for efficient harvesting deep web interfaces. Smart Crawler performs site-based searching for center pages by using search engines, avoiding visiting a large number of pages. To achieve more accurate results for a focused crawl, Smart Crawler techniques prioritize websites to highly relevant ones for a given topic. Smart Crawler achieves fast in-site searching by finding most relevant links with an adaptive link-ranking. To eliminate bias on visiting some relevant links in hidden web directories, author has designed a link tree data structure to achieve wider coverage for a website.

KEYWORDS: Deep web, two-stage crawler, feature selection, ranking, adaptive learning.

INTRODUCTION

The hidden web refers to the contents lie behind searchable web interfaces that cannot be indexed by searching engines. It is estimated that the deep web contains approximately 91,850 terabytes and the surface web is only about 167 terabytes in 2003 [1]. In recent years studies estimated that 1.9 zettabytes were reached and 0.3 zettabytes were consumed worldwide in 2007 [2], [3]. A significant portion of this huge amount of data is estimated to be stored as structured or Relational data in web databases — deep web makes up about 96% of all the content on the Internet, which is 500 to 550 times greater than the surface web [5], [6]. It is an challenge to locate the deep web databases, because they are not registered with any search engines, are usually sparsely distributed, and constantly changing. To address this problem, previous work has proposed two types of crawlers, generic crawlers and focused crawlers. Generic crawlers [10], [11], [12], [13], [14] fetch all searchable forms and cannot focus on a specific topic.

Focused crawlers such as Form-Focused Crawler (FFC) [15] and Adaptive Crawler for Hidden-web Entries (ACHE) [16] can automatically search online databases on a specific topic. Crawler must produce a large quantity of high-quality results from the most relevant content sources [15], [16], [18], [19], [20], [21]. For assessing quality source, Source ranks the results from the selected sources by computing the agreement between them [20], [21]. When selecting a relevant subset from the available content sources, the set of retrieved forms is very heterogeneous. Thus it is crucial to develop smart crawling strategies that are able to quickly discover relevant content sources from the deep web as much as possible. We propose an effective deep web harvesting framework, namely Smart Crawler, for achieving both wide coverage and high efficiency for a focused crawler. Our crawler is divided into two stages: site locating and in-site exploring.

RELATED WORK

Previous work has proposed a number of techniques and tools, including deep web understanding and integration [10], [24], [25], [26], [27], hidden web crawlers [18], [28], [29], and deep web samplers [30], [31], [32]. For all these approaches, the ability to crawl deep web is a key challenge. Crawling deep web has three steps: locating deep web content sources, selecting relevant sources and extracting underlying content [19].

LOCATING DEEP WEB CONTENT SOURCES

Generic crawlers are mainly developed for characterizing deep web and directory construction of deep web resources that do not limit search on a specific topic, but attempt to fetch all searchable Forms [10], [11], [12], [13], [14]. The Database Crawler in the MetaQuerier [10] is designed for automatically discovering query interfaces. Database Crawler first finds root pages by an IP-based sampling, and then performs shallow crawling to crawl pages within a web server starting from a given root page. The IP based sampling ignores the fact that one IP address may have several virtual hosts [11], thus missing many websites. To overcome the drawback of IP based sampling in the Database Crawler, Denis et al. propose a stratified random sampling of hosts to characterize national deep web [13], using the Host graph provided by the Russian search engine Yandex. I-Crawler [14] combines prequery and post-query approaches for classification of searchable forms.

SELECTING RELEVANT SOURCES

Available hidden web directories [34], [8], [7] tends to have low coverage for relevant online databases [23], which restricts their ability in satisfying data access needs [35]. Focused crawler is developed to visit links to pages of interest. The classifier learns to classify pages as search-relevant or not and gives priority to links in search relevant pages. The baseline classifier gives

its choice as feedback so that the apprentice can learn the features of relevant links and prioritize links in the frontier. The FFC [15] and ACHE [16] are focused crawlers used for searching interested deep web interfaces. The FFC comprises of three classifiers, a page classifier that scores the relevance of retrieved pages with a specific topic, a link classifier that prioritizes the links that may lead to pages with searchable forms, and a form classifier that filters out non-searchable forms. ACHE improves FFC with an adaptive link learner and automatic feature selection. Source Rank [20], [21] assesses the relevance of deep web sources during retrieval. Based on an agreement graph, Source Rank calculates the stationary visit probability of a random walk to rank results. Smart Crawler is a domain-specific crawler for locating relevant deep web content sources. Instead of simply classifying links as relevant or not, Smart Crawler first ranks sites and then prioritizes links within a site with another ranker.

SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

PROPOSED SYSTEM:

Author has proposed a two-stage framework, namely Smart Crawler, for efficient harvesting deep web interfaces and second time smart crawler is used as a fast in site searching. Mainly in the first stage, Smart Crawler performs site-based searching for main pages with the help of search engines. In the second stage, Smart Crawler achieves fast in-site searching by digging most relevant links with an adaptive link-ranking. To eliminate bias on visiting some highly relevant links in hidden web directories. Author has designed, a link tree data structure to achieve wider coverage for a website.

TWO STAGE ARCHITECTURE OF SMART CRAWLER:

For effectively discovering deep web data sources, Smart Crawler is designed with a two stage architecture, *site* locating and in-site exploring, as shown in Fig. No. 1. The first site locating stage finds the most relevant site for a given topic, and then in next phase second in-site explores searchable forms from the site. Seeds sites plays an important role of finding candidate sites can be given for Smart Crawler to start crawling, which begins by different URLs from chosen seed sites to explore other pages and domains. Smart crawler comes with a capability of “reverse searching” when the number of unvisited URLs in the database is less than a threshold during the crawling process. Site Frontier is designed to fetch homepage of different URLs from the site database, which are ranked and prioritize by Site Ranker on basis of relevant sites. The Site Ranker comes with a ability of an Adaptive Site Learner, which adaptively learns from features of deep-web sites. To achieve more accurate results for a focused crawl, Site Classifier categorizes URLs into relevant or irrelevant for a given topic based on the homepage content.

Fig. No.2. Adaptive learning process in smart crawler

RANKING MECHANISM:

Smart Crawler uses a site URLs for prioritizing potential deep sites for a relevant topic, while doing ranking two main aspects are taken into consideration are site similarity and site visit frequency. Site similarity assesses the topic similarity between a new site and known deep web sites. Site frequency assessment parameter depends on the frequency site to appear in other sites, which are available again assesses the popularity and authority of the site.

For prioritizing links of a site, the link similarity is computed based on a similarly to the site similarity described above.

CONCLUSION & FUTURE WORK

In this paper author had proposed, an effective harvesting framework for deep-web interfaces, namely Smart- Crawler. Author had proven that approach achieves both wide coverage for deep web interfaces and maintains highly efficient crawling. Experimental results on a representative set of domains shows the effectiveness of the proposed two-stage crawler, which achieves higher harvest rates than other crawlers. In future, we plan to combine pre-query and post-query approaches for classifying deep-web forms to improve the accuracy of the form classifier.

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